

Synthesis and characterization of cardo copolyester of 9,9'-bis(4-hydroxy phenyl) anthrone-10 and 1,1'-bis(R,4-hydroxy phenyl) cyclohexane with terephthaloyl chloride

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Manuscript received 20 August 2003, revised 24 February 2005, accepted 23 March 2005

Cardo copolyesters of (50 : 50 mole compositions) 9,9'-bis(4-hydroxy phenyl) anthrone-10 and 1,1'-bis (R,4-hydroxy phenyl) cyclohexane with terephthaloyl chloride (CP-1 : R = H and CP-2 : R = CH₃) have been synthesized by interfacial polycondensation technique by using water-chloroform as an interphase, alkali as an acid acceptor and sodium lauryl sulfate and benzyl dimethyl hexadecyl ammonium chloride as mixed emulsifiers at 0°C for 4 h. Cardo copolyesters are characterized by IR and NMR spectral data, viscosity, chemical resistance and density. CP-1 and CP-2 possess excellent solubility in common solvents and hydrolytic stability and good thermal stability (345–350°C).

Chemical structure of the polymers is of prime importance in determining various physico-chemical properties. The properties of the base polymers are modified by physical blending, co-polymerization, grafting, or by chemical modifications. The presence of cardo (Latin meaning a loop) groups in rigid chain aromatic polymers are responsible for increasing thermal stability together with excellent solubility in common solvents, processibility, hydrolytic stability, dielectric, mechanical and electrical properties, high T_g , high melting point, heat distortion temperature, impact and flexural strength^{1,2}. They find their applications as thermo-plastic molding parts (gaskets, gear tubing and casting), films, fibers, coatings, adhesive materials, fire proofing, lacquers and paints. The aim of the present work is to synthesize and characterize new copolyesters containing cyclohexyl and anthrone-10 as cardo groups.

CP-1

CP-2

Results and discussion

Copolymer composition : IR (KBr pellets) and NMR (CDCl₃) spectra of CP-1 and CP-2 are presented in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively. Table 1 shows the characteristic IR absorption bands (cm⁻¹) besides aliphatic, alkyl and aromatic groups; and NMR chemical shifts, types of protons and their multiplicity and coupling constant (J) of CP-1 and

Fig. 1. IR spectra (KBr pellet) of CP-1 and CP-2.

Fig. 2. NMR spectra (300 MHz) of CP-1 and CP-2 in CDCl₃.

CP-2. The signal due to residual chloroform is appeared at about 7.26 ppm and overlapped with aromatic protons. In order to determine copolymer compositions, the protons due to BC/MeBC and BAN moieties are identified and integrated peak areas are utilized for the calculation of copolymer compositions according to following relationships :

$$\text{Composition} = \frac{\text{Peak areas of BAN protons}}{\text{Peak areas of BC/MeBC protons}}$$

For CP-1 :

$$\text{Composition} = \frac{(1/3)A1 + A2 + A3 + A4 + (1/2)A5}{(1/2)A5 + A6 + A7}$$

For CP-2 :

$$\text{Composition} = \frac{(1/3)A1 + A2 + (1/8)A3}{(3/8)A3 + A4 + A5 + A6}$$

The observed integrated peak areas for BAN protons are 85.1 and 84.1, respectively for CP-1 and CP-2; and for

Table 1. The IR and NMR spectral data of CP-1 and CP-2

Polymer	Characteristic IR absorption bands (cm ⁻¹)	NMR chemical shifts (ppm)
CP-1	1739.7 (C=O str.)	1.599 (6H, d, β + γ-CH ₂ -)
	1261.4 (C-O str.)	2.318 (4H, s, α-CH ₂ -)
	1668.3 (C=O str. ketone)	7.161–7.103 [8H, m, Ar-H (a + b + h + i), J = 9.6]
		7.256–7.215 [2H, m, Ar-H (f), J = 7.7]
		7.375–7.345 [2H, d, Ar-H (d), J = 8.7]
CP-2		7.571–7.456 [2H, m, Ar-H (e), J = 7.0]
		8.336–8.300 [6H, d, Ar-H (c + g), J = 10.8]
	1739.7 (C=O str.)	1.586 (6H, d, β + γ-CH ₂ -)
	1261.4 (C-O str.)	2.269–2.212 (10H, d, α-CH ₂ - + -CH ₃)
	1670.3 (C=O str. ketone)	7.259–7.071 [16H, m, Ar-H (a + b + h + i + j), J = 8.1]
		7.545–7.436 [4H, m, Ar-H (d + e), J = 6.9]
		8.329–8.295 [6H, t, Ar-H (c + g), J = 5.2]

BC and MeBC moieties they are 76.3 and 87.1, respectively. The calculated copolymer compositions are 1.11 and 0.96, respectively for CP-1 and CP-2, which are in good agreement with the expected compositions.

Viscosity measurements : Viscosity of a solution is a transport property and is a measure of the hydrodynamic volume of a macromolecule. It also furnishes information pertaining to polymer-solvent interactions and thus behavior of polymer chains in the solutions. The intrinsic viscosity [η] of CP-1 and CP-2 were determined in chloroform (CF), 1,2-dichloroethane (DCE) and tetrahydrofuran (THF) at 30°C. The observed [η] values for CP-1 in CF, DCE and THF are 0.26, 0.24 and 0.37 dl/g and for CP-2 they are 0.36, 0.34 and 0.49 dl/g. From these values, it is clear that CP-1 and CP-2 have low intrinsic viscosities indicating moderate molecular weights and as a result they formed brittle films from the solutions. On the basis of [η] values, thermodynamic goodness of the solvents is THF > DCE > CF. CP-2 possesses some what high [η] than that of CP-1 indicating more reactive nature of MeBC moiety.

Homo polyesters of BC and BAN with TC are soluble in the mixture of sym-tetrachloroethane-phenol. In present case the copolymers possess excellent solubility in com-

mon solvents. The preparation of amorphous polymers, decrease of the rigidity of the macromolecular chain, introduction of polar groups showing affinity for the solvent, introduction of various units in the backbone chain and introduction of dissimilar units are the factors responsible for the better solubility. A decrease in the rigidity lowers the heat resistance and hence increases the solubility. It is expected that BAN moiety is comparatively more rigid than BC moiety. Both the homo polyesters are prepared by high temperature polycondensation, while we followed interfacial polycondensation but we failed to obtain high molecular weight polymers. Thus, solubility is improved by combined effect of the said factors at the cost of thermal resistance. In our earlier work² we have improved the solubility of BC-TC homopolymer by introducing dissimilar isophthaloyl group.

Chemical resistance : The resistance to hydrolytic attack of CP-1 and CP-2 films was determined by a change in weight method at room temperature in pure water and 10% each of aqueous hydrochloric acid, sulfuric acid, nitric acid, acetic acid, sodium hydroxide, potassium hydroxide and sodium chloride solutions after 24 h, one week and one month. The observed percent weight gained or loss for CP-1 and CP-2 is found to be $\pm 1.1\%$ indicating excellent hydrolytic stability towards said reagents. A slight loss in weight is due to surface degradation while gain in weight is due to solvation of ions with polar groups present in the polymer chains. In accordance to other cardo polymers², CP-1 and CP-2 possess excellent chemical resistance to acids, alkalis and salt solutions².

Density measurements : The densities of CP-1 and CP-2 films were determined by floatation method using CCl_4 -n-hexane system at room temperature. The observed density values for CP-1 and CP-2 are 1.2619 ± 0.0040 and $1.2403 \pm 0.0009 \text{ g/cm}^3$, respectively. The density of CP-2 is slightly lower due to presence of methyl group. CP-1 is symmetric polymer while CP-2 is asymmetric polymer, which causes lowering of density due to loose packing of the chains.

Thermal properties : DTA and TG thermograms of CP-1 and CP-2 at the heating rate of $15^\circ/\text{min}$ in nitrogen atmosphere are presented in Figs. 3 and 4, respectively. DSC thermograms of CP-1 and CP-2 are not presented here. DSC thermograms showed endothermic transitions at about 475°C (CP-1), 414°C and 457°C (CP-2), which is due to decomposition of copolymers and are supported by weight loss in TG thermograms over those temperature ranges. DTA thermogram of CP-1 showed an exothermic transition at about 494°C , which is due to some disorder-order rearrangement and is supported by no weight change at this tempera-

Fig. 3. DTA thermograms of CP-1 and CP-2 at the heating rate of $15^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ in an N_2 atmosphere.

Fig. 4. TG thermograms of CP-1 and CP-2 at the heating rate of $15^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ in an N_2 atmosphere.

ture region in TG curve. Other DTA exothermic transitions at about 572°C (CP-1) and 531°C (CP-2) are due to decomposition of the compound formed previously as a result of free radicals formed in first step degradation reaction.

CP-1 and CP-2 are thermally stable up to about 345–350°C and involved two-step decomposition. The rapid weight loss is observed over the temperature ranges of 345–481°C and 546–598°C for CP-1 with 24.3 and 38.5% weight loss and temperature of maximum weight loss of 456.1° and 570°C, respectively for first and second steps, while the rapid weight loss is observed over 350–429°C and 490–582°C for CP-2 with 14.3 and 65.8%, weight loss and T_{\max} of 417.9° and 531.4°C, respectively for first and second steps. Kinetic parameters are not determined due to overlapping of two steps in TG thermograms. The presence of methyl group did not affect thermal stability but it has lowered T_{\max} to a considerable extent.

It is expected that homo polyester of BAN-TC must be more thermally resistant than that of BC-TC homo polyester. It has high softening temperature (365–400°C)¹. BC-TC homo polyester² is thermally stable up to about 400°C, while BC-TC-IC copolymers are thermally stable up to about 300°C. The thermal stability must be intermediate of the parent homo polymers. Thus, in present case the rigidity of the polymer chains is lowered by copolymerization of two different cardo bisphenols and also by introducing dissimilarity in the aromatic rings. A shallow and broad endothermic transition for CP-1 and CP-2 are observed over the temperature range 250–325°C, which might be due to the softening temperature as it is preclude from high softening temperatures of BC-TC (380°C) and BAN-TC (365–400°C) homo polyesters. Similarly a large shift in base line is observed in DTA thermograms over the temperature range 250–325°C, which might be due to softening temperature and it is less than BC-TC (380°C) and BAN-TC (365–400°C) homo polyesters.

Degradation of polymers is complex process and involves a variety of reactions such as segmental decomposition, cross-linking, branching, etc. Ester linkages in the main chain and methyl side substituent are weak points, which degrade selectively and free radicals may form. These free radicals may further recombine to form new compound(s), which degrade at higher temperature.

In conclusion copolyesters possess excellent solubility in common organic solvents at the cost of thermal stability and excellent resistance to hydrolytic attack towards acids, alkalis and salt solutions; and good thermal stability.

Experimental

Materials : The chemicals used were of laboratory grade and purified prior to their use. 9,9'-Bis(4-hydroxy phenyl) anthrone-10 (BAN)³. 1,1'-bis (R,4-hydroxy phenyl) cyclohexane (BC : R = H and MeBC : R = CH₃)⁴. terephthaloyl chloride (TC)⁵ were synthesized according to reported methods. BC and MeBC were recrystallized repeatedly from benzene and water-methanol systems, while TC was recrystallized from chloroform-n-hexane system. The emulsifiers benzyl dimethyl hexadecyl ammonium chloride (Fluka A.G.) and sodium lauryl sulfate (Sisco-Chem.) were used as received.

Polymer synthesis : A 0.0025 mole BAN and a 0.0025 mole BC/MeBC were dissolved in 50 ml of 0.012 mole aqueous sodium hydroxide and cooled to 0°C. To this mixture 50 mg benzyl dimethyl hexadecyl ammonium chloride and 50 mg sodium lauryl sulfate were added and emulsion was stirred vigorously for about 15 min. A solution of 0.005 mole TC in 12.5 ml chloroform was added drops wise over 10 min. The emulsion was stirred vigorously for 4 h at 0°C and the polymer was isolated from a large excess of methanol. The separated polymer was filtered washed well with water and finally with methanol and dried at 50°C. The yield was ~83–85%. CP-1 and CP-2 were purified repeatedly from chloroform-methanol system. CP-1 and CP-2 are soluble in common solvents such as chloroform, 1,2-dichloroethane, 1,4-dioxan, THF, DMF, DMSO, etc. CP-1 and CP-2 formed brittle films from chloroform solutions due to their low molecular weights.

Measurements : The IR spectra (KBr pellets) of CP-1 and CP-2 were scanned on a Carl Zeiss Specord FTIR spectrophotometer. The NMR spectra of copolyesters were scanned on a Bruker FTNMR (300 MHz) spectrometer by using CDCl₃ as a solvent and TMS as an internal standard. The density measurements were carried out by floatation method⁶ at room temperature. The viscosity measurements at 30°C were carried out with an Ubbelohde type suspended level viscometer and the intrinsic viscosities were determined by Huggins relationship. The hydrolytic stability of copolymer films were carried out at room temperature for varying period in water, 10% each of acids (HCl, H₂SO₄, HNO₃ and CH₃COOH), alkalis (NaOH and KOH) and NaCl solutions. The TG-DTA (15°C/min) and DSC (10°C/min) measurements were made on Mettler TS systems in an N₂ atmosphere.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Prof. A. R. Parikh, Head, Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University for facilities

and Directors, RSIC, Chandigarh and Nagpur University for testing.

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